

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT REFORMS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS OF THE NON-PHILOLOGICAL DIRECTION

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Abstract. *This article discussed the analysis of the reforms carried out in teaching English to students studying in the non-philological direction. Also, the word brogan about the incomparable importance of the English language in the current developing XXI century, that is, in the age of technology.*

Keywords: *PQ-resolution 1875, PQ-resolution 5117, ESP, EGP, Alan Waters and Tom Hutchinson, Dudlin Evans.*

The 21st century is a century of Information Communication, globalization and advanced pedagogical technologies. This, in turn, is a Age of competition in all areas, and the socio-economic, scientific and technological progress of this century necessitates the modernization of the educational system. To improve the effectiveness of the educational process in our country, the need arose to use modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies.

The decision of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages” dated December 10, 2012 PQ-1875 was one of the most positive changes in modern primary education. In accordance with this decision, the teaching of reading and grammar in the 1st grade of secondary schools began in stages, both oral and play, and from the 2nd grade. From the 2013-2014 school year, the implementation of incomparable work on the further development of English language learning has been initiated. That is, the current implementation of the decision was ensured, and provided textbook and educational and methodological complexes were created in proportion to the age and interests of grades 1 and 2.

The demand for learning a foreign language, especially English, is increasing day by day in the age of technology, which is developing in the current rapid pictures. That is why a lot of significant work is being done in this regard in our country. The study of English is not only the task of linguists, but also representatives of other

fields, in order to achieve a high result in their career, the study of English is being put as a requirement of the Times. For this reason, a lot of attention is paid to teaching and teaching English to students of a non-philological orientation. As proof of our word, the decision of President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev “on measures to bring the activity of popularizing the study of foreign languages to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan” PQ-5117 of May 19, 2021 was signed and the implementation began in practice. According to this decision, by the 2024/2025 academic year, 50% of teachers of professional Sciences (except foreign language direction) operating in state oil educational institutions are set to ensure that at least B2 Darja has national and equivalent international certificates, digitize the teaching of foreign languages, widely introduce modern information and communication technologies necessary for the industry. Now not only linguists, but also representatives of other spheres can learn English for the future prospect of their profession, and this science is called ESP (English for special purposes) in the language of science. This is now a new concept that is very different from teaching English for the general purposes we are currently learning, and is much more complex than EGP (English for general purposes), which also requires a lot of training and labor from both the teacher and the student. The emergence of ESP goes back to the main 3 reasons according to foreign experiments.

The first was the demand of the Times, that is, the end of World War II, which led to an expansion of international and economic

relations, which resulted in an increase in the prestige of the United States at the international level and the mass use of English. The latter caused the emergence and development of linguistic Sciences, that is, oil shortages in Western countries, to begin to penetrate into other countries not only their wealth, but also their knowledge. As a result, English began to be taught as a subject in other countries.

The latest is an increase in emphasis on language learners, which means that language teaching techniques are not simply ignored, but have begun to apply different educational strategies based on the demands and needs of language learners. "English for special purposes (ESP) is a teaching built on the basis of English language (EGP) knowledge for general purposes, and in order to fulfill the specific goals of students, education is intended to prepare on the English language used in the sciences or professions," comments Thomas Orr. We can say that this is a very correct idea, the reason is that before teaching ESP, we definitely need fundamental knowledge that is, EGP. Another linguistic scholar, Peter Strevens, defines ESP as a special purpose language teaching system and lists 4 features to it, has: requirements designed to meet the needs of students, the relationship of English teaching to specific subjects, specializations and professions, the focus on analyzing language and speech exercises, the distinction of teaching ESP from teaching English for general purposes.

On May 6, 2021, at the initiative of the head of state, a videoselector was held, at which

the main topic discussed was the higher ta; it was noted that lim graduates should know at least 2 foreign languages. It was also recognized that this is the right time to establish a new system of teaching foreign languages to achieve this result.

Students of the undergraduate stage of higher education institutions, the specialization of which is not a foreign language, are required to master English at the B2 level. Therefore, effective reforms are being implemented by the government to teach foreign languages to students of non-philological orientation.

In the process of teaching English for special i.e. professional purposes, first of all, the idea of taking into account the needs of language learners, studying and analyzing them is advanced. As a result, the term ESP was first coined in the 80s of the 20th century by Alan Waters and Tom Hutchinson. The main purpose of this style of teaching is to choose educational materials suitable for the psychological age of students, as well as to learn English as a communicator. Dudlin Evans and other scientists, on the other hand, noted that when teaching English to students of a non-philological orientation, it is necessary to focus on completing two methodological tasks: analyzing the current situation (Present situation analysis) and analyzing the content of learning a foreign language (Context analysis). In the theory of implementation and teaching of ESP by scientists, 3 basic principles are distinguished: professional orientation of educational content, efficiency in the educational process, students' interests in science.

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